

Simplified Leakage Treatment for Efficient Kinetics Calculations in Heterogeneous Geometries

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ABSTRACT

An efficient kinetics calculation method using a simplified leakage coefficient matrix that reproduces the original neutron balance is developed based on diffusion calculations. The present method introduces a coefficient that reproduces the total net neutron leakage from each region. Neutron leakage is represented by a simplified diagonal matrix. This makes the memory management of the leakage term easier while reproducing the neutron balance. It is a great advantage in the large heterogeneous geometries, where the leakage term in such geometry becomes complicated due to the varying number of adjacent regions depending on the shape of the regions. The present method is combined with the recently developed efficient factorization method for kinetics calculations, adaptive time-dependent proper orthogonal decomposition (TPOD). The accuracy of the present approach is verified in the TWIGL benchmark problem. As a result, the present method accurately reproduces the original neutron balance at each time step. It demonstrates the effectiveness of the present approach, which is expected to simplify the memory management in time-dependent heterogeneous calculations and increase its computational efficiency.

Keywords: reactor kinetics, proper orthogonal decomposition (POD), equivalent leakage matrix

1. INTRODUCTION

Factorization methods are known as efficient kinetics calculation techniques. Conventionally, the improved quasi-static (IQS) method [1], the multigrid amplitude function (MAF) method [2]–[3], and the transient multilevel (TML) scheme [4] achieve faster computation than conventional methods while keeping accuracy. These methods effectively utilize the benefit of the faster computations, such as the point-kinetics equation and time-dependent coarse mesh finite difference (TCMFD) calculations. Recently, an efficient factorization method, adaptive time-dependent proper orthogonal decomposition (TPOD), has been developed [5]. In the adaptive TPOD, the conventional TCMFD calculations employed in the MAF method and the TML scheme are replaced with the fine time step calculations using POD. It provides finer spatial resolution in fine time step calculations, which is represented by the proper orthogonal basis with fewer degrees of freedom (DOF). Thus, the spatial homogenization is no longer necessary in the adaptive TPOD.

However, when we apply the adaptive TPOD to the time-dependent transport calculations using the method of characteristics (MOC), it poses a new challenge for the memory management because the neutron balance among the unstructured meshes must be represented in a matrix form to apply POD.

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While the previous study [6] has overcome this issue by employing a diffusion calculation corrected by the transport calculation, the leakage matrix is still necessary, similarly to the TCMFD calculations. Since the unstructured meshes make the leakage matrix an irregularly arranged, large, sparse matrix, the cache efficiency also decreases. Thus, a simpler and efficient leakage matrix representation that reproduces the original neutron balance is desirable.

To address this issue, the present study introduces a more simplified yet accurate leakage matrix representation. In the present study, a coefficient that reproduces the total leakage in each region is introduced. Then, the leakage matrix for the finite-difference equation is converted into a diagonal matrix to simplify the memory management for the leakage term. The theoretical basis of the present approach is verified in a diffusion calculation with the structured meshes using the TWIGL benchmark problem [7].

The following sections are organized as follows: Section 2 provides a theoretical basis for the present approach and the adaptive TPOD. Section 3 presents the calculation results for the TWIGL benchmark problem. Finally, Section 4 contains the concluding remarks.

2. NUMERICAL THEORY

2.1. Equivalent leakage matrix construction

In the present study, coefficients that reproduce the total net leakage for each region are introduced to construct a simplified leakage coefficient matrix. The discretized diffusion equation is described as:

$$\sum_{r'} \frac{J_{g,r \rightarrow r'} S_{r' \rightarrow r}}{V_r} + \Sigma_{r,g,r} \phi_{g,r} = Q_{g,r}, \quad (1)$$

where r and r' denote the sequential numbers assigned to each region. $S_{r' \rightarrow r}$ denotes the surface area between region r and r' ; V_r denotes the volume of the region. $\Sigma_{r,g,r}$, $\phi_{g,r}$, and $Q_{g,r}$ denote g -th energy group removal cross section, scalar flux, and neutron source including fission and scattering, respectively. $J_{g,r' \rightarrow r}$ is neutron current, which is described as follows with the finite difference method:

$$J_{g,r \rightarrow r'} = L_{g,r \rightarrow r'} (\phi_{g,r'} - \phi_{g,r}), \quad (2)$$

where $L_{g,r \rightarrow r'}$ denotes the coefficient for net leakage from r to r' . The neutron balance equation is also described in a matrix form as:

$$(\mathbf{L}_g + \mathbf{\Sigma}_{r,g}) \vec{\phi}_g = \vec{Q}_g, \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{L}_g denotes the coefficient matrix for net leakage; $\mathbf{\Sigma}_{r,g}$ denotes the diagonal matrix for the removal cross section. In heterogeneous geometries, the coefficient matrix \mathbf{L}_g becomes a complicated structure because the number of adjacent regions depends on the shape of the region. Thus, the present study introduces the following coefficient that reproduces the total net neutron leakage in each region:

$$L_{g,r} = \frac{1}{\phi_{g,r}} \sum_{r'} \frac{J_{g,r' \rightarrow r} S_{r' \rightarrow r}}{V_r}. \quad (4)$$

By substituting Eq. (1) into Eq. (4), the equivalent leakage coefficient ($L_{g,r}$) can be calculated as follows if the spatially converged flux and neutron source are known:

$$L_{g,r} = \frac{Q_{g,r}}{\phi_{g,r}} - \Sigma_{r,g,r} \quad (5)$$

The equivalent leakage matrix (ELM), \mathbf{E}_g , is defined as:

$$\mathbf{E}_g \equiv \text{diag}(\dots L_{g,r} \dots) \quad (6)$$

Note that the coefficient in the ELM is a function of the scalar flux in each region. It guarantees the original neutron balance only at a specific scalar flux, $\phi_{g,r}$. However, in such a specific state, the complicated leakage matrix can be replaced by a simplified diagonal ELM as:

$$\mathbf{L}_g \vec{\phi}_g = \mathbf{E}_g \vec{\phi}_g \quad (7)$$

Figure 1 shows the arrangement of the non-zero elements of the conventional leakage matrix in 2D diffusion calculation with structured meshes and the ELM. The ELM significantly simplifies the memory management of the leakage term. The next section provides an efficient calculation scheme using the ELM and the adaptive TPOD.

Figure 1. Leakage matrix structures.

2.2. Adaptive TPOD with equivalent leakage matrix

The adaptive TPOD is a calculation scheme that employs the proper orthogonal basis constructed on the fly using the flux distributions around the target time step. The basic concept of the adaptive TPOD is to separate the neutron balance equation into "the fine time step kinetics calculation using POD" and "the coarse time step kinetics calculation for orthogonal basis construction". Figure 2 shows the coarse and fine time steps. Figure 3 illustrates the concept of the adaptive TPOD.

Figure 2. Fine and coarse time steps.

Figure 3. Basic concept of the adaptive TPOD scheme.

In the coarse time step calculation, full order model (FOM) calculation is carried out with coarse time step size (Δt_N). It aims to reduce the number of computationally expensive calculations by increasing the time step. Once the coarse time step calculation is spatially converged, the flux distribution at the current coarse time step ($\vec{\phi}_g^N$) is obtained. Using the flux distributions at current and previous coarse time steps, the solution space of the flux distributions from $t = t_{N-1}$ to t_N is spanned as:

$$\mathbf{M}_g \equiv (\vec{\phi}_g^N \quad \vec{\phi}_g^{N-1}). \quad (8)$$

While the number of flux vectors spanning the solution space is arbitrary in adaptive TPOD, two steps are employed in the present study for simplification. Applying the singular value decomposition (SVD) to the solution space,

$$\mathbf{M}_g = \mathbf{U}_g \mathbf{S}_g \mathbf{V}_g^T, \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{U}_g , \mathbf{S}_g , and \mathbf{V}_g are the left singular vectors, singular values, and right singular vectors, respectively. Since the left singular vectors represent the orthogonal basis for the flux variation from $t = t_{N-1}$ to t_N , we can construct a reduced-order kinetics equation for a fine time step (Δt_n) using POD as:

$$\left(\hat{\mathbf{L}}_g + \hat{\Sigma}_{r,g}^n + \frac{1}{v_g \Delta t_n} \mathbf{I} \right) \vec{\varphi}_g^n = \vec{q}_g^n + \frac{1}{v_g \Delta t_n} \vec{\varphi}_g^{n-1}, \quad (10)$$

where v_g denotes the neutron velocity. \mathbf{I} denotes the identity matrix. $\vec{\varphi}_g^n$ denotes the expansion coefficients of the flux distributions at fine time step, n . \vec{q}_g^n denotes the expansion coefficient of the neutron source, including scattering, prompt, and delayed fissions. The coefficient matrices are described as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{L}}_g = \mathbf{U}_g^T \mathbf{L}_g \mathbf{U}_g, \quad (11)$$

$$\hat{\Sigma}_{r,g}^n = \mathbf{U}_g^T \Sigma_{r,g} \mathbf{U}_g. \quad (12)$$

This dimensionality reduction is significant since the coefficient matrices are reduced from $R \times R$ to 2×2 , where R denotes the number of regions in the FOM. The production cross section, fission spectrum, and scattering cross section that are included in the source term (\vec{q}_g^n) are also compressed into 2×2 matrices in a similar manner [5]. Since the coefficient matrices at coarse time steps are known in the coarse time step calculation, the compressed coefficient matrices at $t = t_{N-1}$ to t_N can be calculated.

Using these matrices, the compressed coefficient matrices at fine time steps are calculated via linear interpolation as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{L}}_g^n = f \hat{\mathbf{L}}_g^N - (1 - f) \hat{\mathbf{L}}_g^{N-1}, \quad (13)$$

$$\hat{\Sigma}_{r,g}^n = f \hat{\Sigma}_{r,g}^N - (1 - f) \hat{\Sigma}_{r,g}^{N-1}, \quad (14)$$

$$f = \frac{t_n - t_{N-1}}{t_N - t_{N-1}}. \quad (15)$$

Once a fine time step calculation from $t = t_{N-1}$ to t_N using the interpolation of the compressed coefficient matrices is carried out, fine time dependence is reflected in the coarse time step calculation.

While the above approach has recently been developed by authors [5], the utilization of the ELM (\mathbf{E}_g) instead of the conventional leakage matrix (\mathbf{L}_g) requires careful implementation because the ELM only guarantees the same neutron balance for the specific flux distribution, which is used to calculate the leakage coefficient described in Eqs. (4) or (5). Thus, when we employ the ELM for the fine time step calculation using POD, the correspondence between \mathbf{E}_g^N and $\vec{\phi}_g^N$, as well as between \mathbf{E}_g^{N-1} and $\vec{\phi}_g^{N-1}$, must be preserved in the dimensionality reduction.

In the present study, the dimensionality reduction for the ELM is derived as follows. First, the orthogonal expansion of the flux distributions is described as follows:

$$\vec{\phi}_g^N = \mathbf{U}_g \vec{\varphi}_g^N = (\vec{u}_{g,0} \quad \vec{u}_{g,1}) (\varphi_{g,0}^N \quad \varphi_{g,1}^N)^T = \vec{u}_{g,0} \varphi_{g,0}^N + \vec{u}_{g,1} \varphi_{g,1}^N, \quad (16)$$

$$\vec{\phi}_g^{N-1} = \mathbf{U}_g \vec{\varphi}_g^{N-1} = \vec{u}_{g,0} \varphi_{g,0}^{N-1} + \vec{u}_{g,1} \varphi_{g,1}^{N-1}, \quad (17)$$

where $\varphi_{g,0}^N$ and $\varphi_{g,1}^N$ denote the 0th and 1st order expansion coefficients for $\vec{\phi}_g^N$, respectively. $\vec{u}_{g,0}$ and $\vec{u}_{g,1}$ denote the 0th and 1st basis vectors, respectively. Then, the basis vectors are solved as follows:

$$\vec{u}_{g,0} = \frac{\varphi_{g,1}^{N-1}}{\varphi_{g,0}^N \varphi_{g,1}^{N-1} - \varphi_{g,1}^N \varphi_{g,0}^{N-1}} \vec{\phi}_g^N - \frac{\varphi_{g,1}^N}{\varphi_{g,0}^N \varphi_{g,1}^{N-1} - \varphi_{g,1}^N \varphi_{g,0}^{N-1}} \vec{\phi}_g^{N-1} = u_0^N \vec{\phi}_g^N + u_0^{N-1} \vec{\phi}_g^{N-1}, \quad (18)$$

$$\vec{u}_{g,1} = \frac{\varphi_{g,0}^{N-1}}{\varphi_{g,0}^{N-1} \varphi_{g,1}^N - \varphi_{g,1}^{N-1} \varphi_{g,0}^N} \vec{\phi}_g^N - \frac{\varphi_{g,0}^N}{\varphi_{g,0}^{N-1} \varphi_{g,1}^N - \varphi_{g,1}^{N-1} \varphi_{g,0}^N} \vec{\phi}_g^{N-1} = u_1^N \vec{\phi}_g^N + u_1^{N-1} \vec{\phi}_g^{N-1}. \quad (19)$$

While the time step of the ELM is considered later, the dimensionality reduction for the ELM is described as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{E}}_g = \mathbf{U}_g^T \mathbf{E}_g \mathbf{U}_g = \begin{pmatrix} \vec{u}_{g,0}^T \\ \vec{u}_{g,1}^T \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{E}_g (\vec{u}_{g,0} \quad \vec{u}_{g,1}) = \begin{pmatrix} E_{00} & E_{01} \\ E_{10} & E_{11} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \vec{u}_{g,0}^T \mathbf{E}_g \vec{u}_{g,0} & \vec{u}_{g,0}^T \mathbf{E}_g \vec{u}_{g,1} \\ \vec{u}_{g,1}^T \mathbf{E}_g \vec{u}_{g,0} & \vec{u}_{g,1}^T \mathbf{E}_g \vec{u}_{g,1} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (20)$$

By substituting Eqs. (18) and (19) into Eq. (20), the matrix element E_{00} is described as:

$$E_{00} = \vec{u}_{g,0}^T \mathbf{E}_g \vec{u}_{g,0} = (u_0^N \vec{\phi}_g^N + u_0^{N-1} \vec{\phi}_g^{N-1})^T \mathbf{E}_g (u_0^N \vec{\phi}_g^N + u_0^{N-1} \vec{\phi}_g^{N-1}). \quad (21)$$

The time step of the ELM must be consistent with the right-hand-side flux vector of the ELM to preserve their correspondence. Thus, Eq. (21) is expanded as:

$$E_{00} = u_0^N u_0^N (\vec{\phi}_g^N)^T \mathbf{E}_g \vec{\phi}_g^N + u_0^N u_0^{N-1} (\vec{\phi}_g^N)^T \mathbf{E}_g^{N-1} \vec{\phi}_g^{N-1} + u_0^{N-1} u_0^N (\vec{\phi}_g^{N-1})^T \mathbf{E}_g \vec{\phi}_g^N + u_0^{N-1} u_0^{N-1} (\vec{\phi}_g^{N-1})^T \mathbf{E}_g^{N-1} \vec{\phi}_g^{N-1}, \quad (22)$$

The remaining matrix elements are calculated in the same manner as:

$$E_{01} = u_0^N u_1^N (\vec{\phi}_g^N)^T \mathbf{E}_g^N \vec{\phi}_g^N + u_0^N u_1^{N-1} (\vec{\phi}_g^N)^T \mathbf{E}_g^{N-1} \vec{\phi}_g^{N-1} + u_0^{N-1} u_1^N (\vec{\phi}_g^{N-1})^T \mathbf{E}_g^N \vec{\phi}_g^N + u_0^{N-1} u_1^{N-1} (\vec{\phi}_g^{N-1})^T \mathbf{E}_g^{N-1} \vec{\phi}_g^{N-1}, \quad (23)$$

$$E_{10} = u_1^N u_0^N (\vec{\phi}_g^N)^T \mathbf{E}_g^N \vec{\phi}_g^N + u_1^N u_0^{N-1} (\vec{\phi}_g^N)^T \mathbf{E}_g^{N-1} \vec{\phi}_g^{N-1} + u_1^{N-1} u_0^N (\vec{\phi}_g^{N-1})^T \mathbf{E}_g^N \vec{\phi}_g^N + u_1^{N-1} u_0^{N-1} (\vec{\phi}_g^{N-1})^T \mathbf{E}_g^{N-1} \vec{\phi}_g^{N-1}, \quad (24)$$

$$E_{11} = u_1^N u_1^N (\vec{\phi}_g^N)^T \mathbf{E}_g^N \vec{\phi}_g^N + u_1^N u_1^{N-1} (\vec{\phi}_g^N)^T \mathbf{E}_g^{N-1} \vec{\phi}_g^{N-1} + u_1^{N-1} u_1^N (\vec{\phi}_g^{N-1})^T \mathbf{E}_g^N \vec{\phi}_g^N + u_1^{N-1} u_1^{N-1} (\vec{\phi}_g^{N-1})^T \mathbf{E}_g^{N-1} \vec{\phi}_g^{N-1}, \quad (25)$$

Using the compressed ELM shown above, the fine time step calculation can be performed without disrupting the neutron balance. Note that the interpolation of the compressed ELM between the coarse time steps is not carried out since Eqs. (22)–(25) satisfy the consistency between the ELM and flux vector, and represent the averaged neutron balance between the coarse time steps. Memory management for the leakage term is also significantly simplified since adjacent regions do not need to be managed in the ELM.

3. VERIFICATION

The TWIGL benchmark problem [7] is calculated to evaluate the accuracy of the present approach. Table I shows the calculation conditions for the present verification. There are 1 reference case and 2 test cases. "REF" denotes the reference case, which employs the conventional fully implicit method with a fine time step size. In the reference case, the leakage term is calculated using the conventional 5-point diagonal matrix (5PDM). In the test cases, "TPOD" and "TPOD-ELM", the adaptive TPOD scheme is employed. The coarse and fine time step sizes are 0.1 sec and 0.001 sec, respectively. The number of time steps used for the construction of the orthogonal bases (N_c) is 2 for both test cases, i.e., flux distributions at the current and previous coarse time steps are used to construct the orthogonal basis. The difference between the test cases, TPOD and TPOD-ELM, is the treatment of the leakage matrix. The ELM is employed for the fine time step POD calculations in TPOD-ELM.

Table I. Calculation conditions.

Case name	REF	TPOD	TPOD-ELM
Time discretization	FI	Adaptive TPOD	Adaptive TPOD
Leakage matrix	5PDM	5PDM	ELM
Time step	0.001 sec	$\Delta t_N = 0.1$ sec, $\Delta t_n = 0.001$ sec	$\Delta t_N = 0.1$ sec, $\Delta t_n = 0.001$ sec
N_c	-	2	2

The calculations in the ramp perturbation condition are carried out using the cross sections specified in the benchmark problem. Table II shows the accuracy of the core power and the root mean square (RMS) difference of the flux distributions compared to the reference solution, which are calculated as follows:

$$\epsilon(\%) = \frac{CP - CP_{ref}}{CP_{ref}} \times 100, \quad (26)$$

$$\text{RMS}(\%) = 100 \times \sqrt{\frac{1}{R} \sum_r^R \left(\frac{\phi_{g,r}^n - \phi_{g,r}^{n,ref}}{\phi_{g,r}^{n,ref}} \right)^2}, \quad (27)$$

Table II. Calculation results of the TWIGL benchmark problem.

Time [sec]	Relative difference for core power [%]		RMS difference for flux dist. [%]	
	TPOD	TPOD-ELM	TPOD	TPOD-ELM
0.0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.1	-0.01	-0.01	0.01	0.01
0.2	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
0.3	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.04
0.4	-0.08	-0.08	0.08	0.08

As shown in Table II, the accuracy of the TPOD and TPOD-ELM is the same, i.e., the ELM successfully reproduces the original neutron balance. Table III shows the computation time for each case. All calculations are carried out by a single thread on Intel® Core™ Ultra 9 285 processor (5.6GHz) with 32GB of memory. The computation times of the TPOD and TPOD-ELM are almost the same.

Table III. Computation time of the TWIGL benchmark problem.

REF	TPOD	TPOD-ELM
17775 msec	555 msec	559 msec

These results demonstrate the effectiveness of the ELM for adaptive TPOD calculations. Since the advantage of the ELM lies in the simplification of the memory management in heterogeneous geometries, the present approach is planned to be applied to time-dependent transport calculations using the method of characteristics (MOC) in a future study. It also involves the treatment of the coefficients corresponding to the flux vectors in Eqs. (18) and (19) for null-transient, i.e., kinetics calculations with zero reactivity, since the denominator of the coefficients becomes zero in such conditions.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, a simplified representation of the leakage term that reproduces the total net leakage for each region is proposed. It aims to simplify the memory management in the fine time step calculations using POD for the adaptive TPOD method. The present study introduces an equivalent leakage matrix (ELM), which is the simplified diagonal matrix using the leakage coefficient that reproduces the total net leakage from each region. To combine the ELM with the adaptive TPOD, a dimensionality reduction preserving the correspondence between the ELM and the flux vector is proposed because the ELM only guarantees the same neutron balance at the corresponding flux distribution. A fundamental verification for the present approach is carried out in the TWIGL benchmark problem. The calculation results of adaptive TPOD with and without the ELM show good

agreement. These results support the effectiveness of the present approach. Future studies will involve the application of the ELM to time-dependent heterogeneous calculations using MOC, including verification in unstructured geometries such as the C5G7-TD benchmark, as well as more realistic reactor problems.

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